

Radiation chemistry in microemulsion

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Radiation chemistry can be used to study reactions of free radicals not only in homogeneous medium but also in micro-heterogeneous medium, microemulsion being typical example of this type of medium. This article intends to summarize some radiation chemical studies in microemulsion using pulse radiolysis as a tool. Attempt has been made to show that the reaction and self-decay of hydrated electron can lead to achieve useful results relating to the physical properties of micro-droplets. Moreover, free radical reactions with biomolecules in these media can sometime be extrapolated to living systems.

The biological membrane, where lipids, proteins and carbohydrates coexist to produce the essential unit of compartmentalization of all living organisms, the cell, is a natural example of self-assembly which increases the efficiency of the biochemical and biophysical processes. Several groups of scientists are engaged in understanding the complex phenomena that occur in these living systems. The inherent complexities of these systems pose a challenge to carry out different types of studies *in vivo*. To get rid of this problem several intelligent model systems have been proposed where physicochemical studies can be carried out and results obtained in these may be extrapolated to living systems. Among these models the use of amphiphilic synthetic surfactants in water/organic solvent media represents a good experimental approach and can serve as a model of biological structures. Normal micelles, reverse micelles, micro-emulsions fall under the category of model systems. During last three decades a number of studies have appeared in journals and have been well reviewed¹⁻¹⁰ regarding the electron and radical processes as well as biochemical reactions in these aggregates. The latest in this series is by Gebicki *et al.*¹¹ where the authors presented both the influence of micro-heterogeneous environment on a variety of processes and the information about organized assemblies themselves with the help of radiation chemical studies. In the present article we will restrict our discussion on microemulsion only with an objective to present some interesting studies carried out in this system in our laboratory.

It is now in general agreement that in biological systems, at the molecular level, free radical-induced reactions form an essential part of many of the degradative processes that afflict life. The free radical damage to cell constituents that carry out critical functions, such as DNA, may have serious biological consequence. Thus it is essential to un-

derstand the free radical processes occurring in or with bio-systems to solve many important issues in physiology and medicine. To achieve this, it is necessary to generate biologically relevant free radicals in model systems. For this purpose the knowledge of radiation chemistry is generally used employing pulse radiolysis as one of the most advanced methods. In short, radiation chemistry deals with the chemical reactions induced by ionizing radiations by breaking up of the medium known as radiolysis. When it passes through water, at first excitation and ionization take place which lead to radical species and molecular products in $\geq 10^{-12}$ s.

Here, the numbers in the parenthesis are yield of the species in micromoles per unit Joule of absorbed energy. These numbers may be converted to the classical *G*-values (unit : species per 100 eV of absorbed energy) by simply multiplying with 9.648. These are called primary radicals. These species are formed, diffuse in the medium, decay and react with other solutes and among themselves in the time-scale of 10^{-9} to 10^{-6} s. The primary radicals are scavenged by using appropriate solutes and gases to generate secondary radicals as per requirement.

The radiation chemistry and hence pulse radiolysis technique in microemulsion can be employed to investigate three fundamental queries : (i) characterization of the aggregate, i.e. size of the water pool, and location of different types of solutes dissolved in this system, (ii) study of biochemical reactions in these membrane mimetic models, and (iii) whether these systems can be used as a novel catalytic medium for synthesis of special materials. The third aspect is now well established¹²⁻¹⁵ and will not be covered in our discussion. In the next section of our discussion focus will be on first two fundamental goals.

Water pool radius and location of probes

Pulse radiolysis technique can be used to determine the size of the water pools and location of the probes in a microemulsion. For this purpose, the kinetics of hydrated electron itself and its reaction with different solutes are exploited. Radiolytic production of hydrated electrons and electron processes in micro-heterogeneous system have been studied during past two decades¹⁶⁻²⁴. Hydroxyl and H radicals are formed by direct radiolysis and as their reaction rate constant with surfactant and co-surfactant (in general long-chain alkyl alcohol) are very high, they are easily scavenged. In general, this limits the study to e_{aq}^- and only secondary radicals produced from this species in water-in-oil microemulsion. However, in micellar and oil-in-water systems, reactions of OH and H radicals can also be studied. There are two sources of hydrated electrons in water-in-oil microemulsion. First one is direct radiolysis of water pools and the second one is scavenging of excess electrons produced in the hydrocarbon phase. The second process has to compete with the annihilation process, i.e. recombination. The efficiency of recombination decreases with the increase in radius of the water pool. The water molecules that are bound to counterion of the surfactant cannot participate in the solvation of electrons.

Wong *et al.*¹⁶ studied electron processes in AOT, heptane and water system and showed that hydrated electrons are not formed below a critical size of the solubilized water pools. Pulse radiolytic formation of electron and its attachment to H₂O-AOT reverse micelles has been studied by Bakale *et al.*¹⁷. They showed that the properties of the bulk water are approached only when H₂O/Na⁺ ratio exceeds 6. Using competition kinetics and CCl₄ as an electron scavenger, they found that the largest water pools have greater attachment rates. It has been clearly shown that the thermal electrons present in the hydrocarbon phase are captured by water pools. The efficiency of electron capture by water pools increases with increasing water pool size, or availability of free non-bonded water molecules in the water pool. The absorption spectra, yield, lifetime and reaction kinetics of hydrated electrons have been well studied in ternary and quaternary microemulsion and have been covered in a recent review¹¹.

Decay kinetics of hydrated electrons can be used to find out the water pool radius and location of the probes. The following discussion is with reference to a microemulsion consisting of SDS/water/1-pentanol/cyclohexane used in our studies^{25,26}. The decay of the hydrated electron in microemulsion obeys the kinetic equation,

$$[e_{aq}^-] = [e_{aq}^-]_0 \exp [-(k_0 + k_e [Q])t] \exp [-\bar{n}[1 - \exp (-k_q t)]] \quad (1)$$

where $[e_{aq}^-]$ and $[e_{aq}^-]_0$ are the hydrated electron concentrations at time t and zero, respectively, k_0 is the first order decay rate constant of the hydrated electron in the absence of solutes, k_e the bimolecular rate constant for an exchange process that involves water pool collisions, k_q the hydrated electron decay constant in the presence of solutes and \bar{n} the average number of solute per micelle; $\bar{n} = [Q] / [WP]$, where $[Q]$ and $[WP]$ are the concentrations of the solute and water pools, respectively. $k_e[Q]$ can be neglected if the hydrated electron lifetime is much shorter than the exchange process, or, if the system is so rigid that, although electrons have their lifetime in microsecond time-scale, they are still unaffected by the exchange process. The latter is true for the present case.

At any given time t , P_0 , the probability of finding zero solute per micelle, is given by

$$P_0 = \frac{[e_{aq}^-] \text{ in the presence of solutes}}{[e_{aq}^-] \text{ in the absence of solutes}} \quad (2)$$

Following the Poisson distribution,

$$\ln P_0 = -\bar{n} = -[Q] / [WP] \quad (3)$$

Hence, a plot of $\ln P_0$ versus $[Q]$ gives a measure of the water pool concentration, which in turn gives the radius of the water pools assuming these are of spherical shape. A typical plot is shown in Fig. 1. In fact there is also an empirical relationship between water pool radius \AA and W_0 ($[H_2O] / [\text{surfactant}]$) as $r = 1.5 W_0$. This empirical formula can be experimentally verified with different types of sol-

Fig. 1. Variation of (■) $\ln P_0$ and (●) $\ln(A'_0/A')$ with BSA concentration at $W_0 = 24$, $t = 3 \mu\text{s}$.

Table 1. Water pool radius (Å) for different W_0 using different solutes

Solute	W_0					
	16	24	32	41	48	60
BSA	27	37	45	57	66	90
<i>N,N</i> -DMF	–	38	46	60	68	93
Cu^{2+}	–	35	45	57	73	–
CCl_4	23	33	50	–	69	88

utes having different molecular size and solvation zone (Table 1).

As the absorbance of the hydrated electrons is directly proportional to the concentration of e_{aq}^- , eqn. (1) reduces to

$$\ln \left(\frac{A_0}{A} \right) = k_0 t + \left(\frac{[Q]}{[\text{WP}]} \right) [1 - \exp(-k_q t)] \quad (4)$$

where, A_0 and A are the absorbances of hydrated electrons at time zero and t , respectively. Now fixing the time at t , eqn. (4) can be written as

$$\ln \left(\frac{A'_0}{A'} \right) = K_1 + [Q]K_2 \quad (5)$$

where A'_0 and A' are the absorbances of the hydrated electrons at time t in the absence and the presence of quenchers,

respectively, $K_1 = k_0 t$ and $K_2 = \frac{1}{[\text{WP}]} [1 - \exp(-k_q t)]$. Now

k_q can be evaluated by plotting $\ln (A'_0 / A')$ versus $[Q]$ at a particular time (Fig. 1).

There can be two cases; one is the solute located in the water pool and the second is the solute located at the interface. If the solute is located in the water pool, k_q is expected to vary with $1/W_0^3$ and for the solute located at the interface, k_q varies with $1/W_0^2$. Hence, the slope of the plot of $\log k_q$ versus $\log W_0$ gives a clue as to the location of the solutes. The slope being close to -2 or -3 means that the solubilization site is at the interface or within the water pool, respectively. Such a typical plot is shown in Fig. 2, which shows that the big protein molecule bovine serum albumin (BSA) stays at the interface up to a certain W_0 , whereas *N,N*-dimethylformamide remains in the aqueous core.^{25,26}

Studies on biochemical reactions in the membrane mimetic media

The aims of this type of studies are of two folds. One is to understand the arrangement of proteins (and enzymes) embedded in the membrane and enzymatic reactions at the membrane interface. The second one is to study free radical (or chemical) reactions of relatively smaller molecules so as

Fig. 2. Variation of $\log k_q$ with $\log W_0$ for the solutes : (a) BSA, (b) *N,N*-dimethylformamide, (c) CuSO_4 , (d) CCl_4 .

to understand their role in different aspects in physiology. Both of these finally need a one-to-one correlation with physiological situation, which is not an easy task. However, research in this direction is in progress with some measure of success.

In literature, results from free radical induced reduction reactions are more available in water-in-oil microemulsion as it is mentioned earlier that the system limits the reaction of solutes with e_{aq}^- , though oxidizing radicals (trichloromethylperoxyl radical, CCl_3OO^*) may also be produced from e_{aq}^- . Visser and Fendler²⁷ reported the reaction of e_{aq}^- with cytochrome C and C_3 in AOT- H_2O -heptane reverse micelle. It has been observed that the presence of a protein in the water pool increases the rate of decay of the hydrated electrons which are rapidly quenched by the protein side-chain and/or other processes before actual reduction occurs, resulting in lowering in the reduction of protein. In a recent study²⁵, it has been shown that interaction between bovine serum albumin and surfactant varies in a size (of the water core) dependent manner. At low W_0 a strong interaction has been observed while as the size increases the protein starts entering into the water core. The bimolecular rate constant for the reaction of the molecules like BSA and lysozyme (Lz) increases steadily as W_0 increases in a NaLS/ H_2O /cyclohexane/1-pentanol system²⁸. Interestingly, on reduction of BSA and Lz, formation of thiyl radical (RS^*) has been

observed, confirmed using dimethyldisulfide (DMDS) as a probe. Reduction studies of proteins in homogeneous aqueous media do not show the thiyl radical formation. All these results indicate that reduction of proteins in micro-environment may take place at a different rate and may follow a different pathway.

Free radical induced oxidation studies in microemulsion are limited in literature citation. A typical study of such kind may be discussed here, the oxidation of β -carotene in microemulsion, a recent work. A few sentences are necessary to explain the background of this particular work. The exact role of β -carotene against cancer risk is still speculative and controversial²⁹, although it is well known as an ubiquitous free radical quencher³⁰⁻³². Indeed, the efficacy of β -carotene as an anticarcinogen and for the prevention of cardiovascular diseases has been attributed to its antioxidant properties in combination with immunomodulatory activity^{33,34}. However, the antioxidant effect is yet to be proven in human. β -Carotene is known as 'provitamin A' due to its conversion into retinol (vitamin A) by the enzyme dioxygenase via its central^{35,36} or eccentric³⁷ cleavage. This has been demonstrated by *in vivo* tests with vitamin A deficient animals³⁸. Surprisingly, although the enzyme is present chiefly in the intestine and possibly in the liver, accumulation of vitamin A has been noticed in many tissues in mice³⁹. This leads to the speculation as to whether it is possible that vitamin A can be derived from β -carotene by some purely chemical protocol. To address this question, β -carotene was subjected to undergo halogenated alkyl peroxy radical induced oxidation generating β -carotene radical cation in a NaLS/water/cyclohexane/1-pentanol system⁴⁰ either via the initial formation of an adduct or by a direct reaction. An additional transient species was also observed in this study as compared to earlier studies, that was probably the transient just prior to the product formation. Moreover, a stable product has been observed which shows the characteristic feature similar to that of retinol. This study confirms that along with many possible products, retinol is formed during free radical induced oxidation of β -carotene in microemulsion. This might also explain the presence of retinol in organs other than the intestine and the liver as found with mice³⁹.

The examples of free radical reactions in microemulsion that have been shown here justifies that some results carried out in these types of media can be extrapolated to living systems. Unfortunately, oxidation studies in microemulsion are limited and have an ample scope for future researchers, though several studies are in progress in other model systems such as liposome, microsome, etc.

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